

Preserving Culture Through Craftsmanship: A Study On Pottery Town In Bengaluru

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Cultural heritage is an important aspect that reflects the identity of a society. It comprises of art, architecture, music, oral traditions, crafts and others. India's rich cultural heritage is reflected through its multilingual ethnicity, dance, festivals, clothing, and cuisine. The above said aspect is applicable to Karnataka, one of the states of India.

Bangalore, the capital city of Karnataka has attracted people following different occupations from various parts of India leading to their settlements in course of time including the potters. Pottery Town in Bangalore is where the potters live and practice their craft. They have moved to Bangalore from Vellore in Tamil Nadu four hundred years ago and they were patronized by the then rulers, Wodeyars of Mysore. The potters of Pottery Town have an urge to preserve this craft by practising as well as imparting knowledge of the same to others.

This paper tries to analyse the various ways and means by which the potters of Pottery Town make efforts to preserve this age old craft. This paper also analyses the life experiences of the families living in Pottery Town and the future scope of this craft.

Keywords: Cultural heritage, Pottery Town, Life Experiences, Preserve, Craft.